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A PRELIMINARY STUDY OF VISION-INDUCED TACTILE ENTICEMENT.

Yu-chen Chen / Min-yuan Ma / Kuo-hsiang Chen
Department of Industrial Design, National Cheng Kung University
lucy75411@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Objects in our daily life contain the ability that arouses people to touch. The research defines it as "Tactile Enticement," and mainly focuses on visual aspect. The research chiefly aimed at finding the cause of Tactile Enticement, and trying to categorize visual characteristics of objects which are enticing to touch. For doing so, 10 subjects were asked to cruise around the shopping mall and touch anything they want, which were recorded. By applying Evaluation Grid Method, the original reasons of why they touch, the solid characteristics of what they noticed and the feeling when they touched would be obtained. The result shows six aspects—Attract Attention, Raise Curiosity, New Experience Provision, Amusing Interaction, Friendly and kind Feeling, and Disapproval that may cause the Tactile Enticement.

Keywords: Tactile enticement, Touch, Vision, Product Design.

INTRODUCTION

There are things in our daily life which are always arousing people to feel like to touch. For example, delicate babies' skin, soft-like sofa, special surface coating for cell phones ...etc. Malls or Exhibition centers may sometimes set up signs: "Don't touch." for their exhibits. However, those things may it selves spread touchable enticements stronger than the signs. This research treats the phenomenon "arousing the feeling to touch" as "Tactile Enticement". The features or the condition of objects, which entice people to touch, are the characteristics of "Tactile Enticement". The research mainly focuses on "Tactile Enticement" that may exist on objects in visual aspect. In order to

have preliminary understanding on the process of "Tactile Enticement", the study chiefly aimed at finding the cause of Tactile Enticement, and trying to categorize visual characteristics of objects which are enticing to touch.

LITERARY REVIEWS

SENSE OF TOUCH

Sense of touch, is the feeling generated when skin surface receive the pressure or contact (Zhang, 1995). It can be divided into:

- Active touch: Touch the object by limb actively.
 - Passive touch: Be pressed by the object.
- The touch defined in this study is "Active touch". Passive touch or will-less touch is not included.

ATTENTION VALUE

Attention Value, as objects to catch attention, was proposed on graphic design on definition of attention (Engel, 1993). The factors to catch attention are two factors: stimulus aspect and human behavior aspect.

In stimulus aspect includes strength, contrast, color, position, information, direction, novelty, and image selectivity. In human behavior aspect contains motivation and attitude.

An object that is eye-catching may not be the same one that people want to touch most, but always be the one with higher chance to be touched.

DEFINITION OF FORM

Lin (2001) extended the definition of form elements, and sort them as shape, color, texture, space and function. Organize as follows:

- Shape: It's the appearance of the object. The shape can be classified as natural shape and artificial shape, or be divided into pure shape and practical shape by usage.
- Color: It's an independent element but full of variety.
- Texture: The structure of materials. Each material has its special texture and composition.
- Space: One is the existence of the object itself; the other is the relative existence relation of two or more objects.
- Function: The functional considerations, that is consistent with using requirements.

The research refers to Lin's definition of form to record and sort the features of objects.

EVALUATION GRID METHOD

A psychologist Kelly (1955) proposed a concept that "Every person is a scientist," which indicates that people keep making assumptions of their world and testifying them. Kelly applies the concept to create "Kelly Repertory Grid Method" (RGM) on clinical psychological therapy. It is a method to obtain subjects' thought by comparing between events or constituents.

Sanui, J. and Inui, M. (1986) adapted RGM and create Evaluation Grid Method (EGM), which mainly used on capturing consumers' preference on products. It is one of the important research methods in Miryoku Engineering. The essence of EGM is comparison. Through comparison with objects during personal interview, the difference and the resemblance are clearly discussed, consecutively sorted the personality of object. Finally, the concept caught up from interview is arranged into grid charts.

EXPERIMENT

The research mainly focuses on "Tactile Enticement" that may exist on objects in visual aspect. The research procedure is simply shown:

- Touch events discovery: subjects were invited to view some exhibits, then the interaction between subjects and objects were observed and recorded to find out the events.

- Interview: By using EGM, subjects were asked to talk about those touched objects.

TOUCH EVENTS DISCOVERY

Location

In order to let the subjects browse multiple types of things to receive different visual stimulation in limited time, the experimental location selected in IKEA furniture in Kaohsiung, Taiwan. Reasons are as follows:

- Free photography.
- Without any disturbance from shop assistant.
- All of the exhibits can be touched.
- With good shopping route.
- Exhibits are diverse.

Process

The subject follows the shopping route to browse the shopping mall. The exhibits in the mall are the experimental samples. The pace of browsing depends on each subject, and the researcher follows up to take photos, for recording those objects touched on subject's own will, including picked up, poked, played or contacted by limbs. These recording photos are the basis of the follow-up interview. In this process, to keep the subject relaxed, the subject is allowed to communicate with the researcher as a friend. But the researcher can't point out or hint any exhibit to be noticed or touched, in order to prevent from affecting subject's judgment.

Pre-procedure

Because knowing the research purpose will interfere in the judgment in whether to approach the exhibits or not, the instruction before experiment doesn't reveal any information about "tactile enticement" or the purpose to subjects. Hence, the subjects were merely informed as to participating "The research of the interaction between humans and objects". In addition, the personal information filled by subject before the experiment includes "The recent want-to-buy product". Subject who touches the want-to-buy products may be purposefully and prepossessively. This is a situation that subject touch the

objects with specific purpose, which differs from receiving visual stimulation first, as the paper mainly discussed.

Subjects

Experimental subjects were 10 in total, 5 males and 5 females, all around 24 to 28 years old younger.

INTERVIEW

After exhibits-browsing experiment, the research purpose is shown to subjects clearly, and the interview starts. The photos, taken when objects were touched by subjects during the experiment, are the stimuli for subjects to recall the memory why they touch the exhibits, and to compare with those they don't touch. The interview refer to Evaluation Grid Method, then the original reasons of why they touch, the solid characteristics of what they noticed and the feeling when they touched would be obtained.

ANALYSIS

Interview was recorded. The contents were then sorted out in hierarchical relations (Figure 1), revealing the reasons why objects were touched. To the left side are mental factors of humans, and to the right are the conditions of objects.

Figure 1. The interview contents were sorted out in hierarchical relations.

Next, all objects were sorted by the original reasons. The objects with the reason, " Touch for buying purpose" was removed. Finally, KJ method was applied refer to original reasons and abstract factors (Figure 2). Six aspects of Tactile Enticement were then categorized (Table 1). They are Attract Attention, Raise Curiosity, New Experience Provision, Amusing Interaction, Friendly and kind Feeling, and Disapproval. The table1 shows the original reasons

and concrete elements of each Tactile Enticement aspect, sort from the elements of EGM.

Figure 2. The process of KJ method.

DISCUSSION

This section shows the discussion in three parts: six aspects of Tactile Enticement, sustainability of Tactile Enticement and the limitation in research.

SIX ASPECTS OF TACTILE ENTICEMENT

Attracting attention

From interview, the objects that attract someone's attention hence were touched usually were accompanied with some motivation. For example, red sofa is eye-catching and meanwhile looks comfortable; strange things catch attention and were touched out of curiosity. Hence, attract attention is sometimes the backstage driving force of happening to Tactile Enticement. Noticeable things have more chance of being touched.

Raising curiosity

Packed products or objects that can't recognize immediately obfuscate subjects hence arouse curiosity to touch them.

In addition, the possibility of hiding something behind or inside such as closet, cabinet, or even curtain may also arouse the curiosity.

New experience Provision

Sense of touch is sometimes irreplaceable and unattainable. For example, a chair with a fresh new looking make people want to give it a try; furry texture let people want to test its softness. When hardness of a texture is unattained by eyes, people tend to try it. Research show the difference between

visual and tactile exists hence sense of touch is irreplaceable (Lu, 2002). Besides, some products that is functional or instruction included are also likely to be tried out.

Amusing interaction

In addition to toys and dolls, objects that is operable

or motion inferred is easy to be touch. Gibson (1979) mentioned, a slim and handy object provide to be swayed, which was observed during the experiment. On the other hand, buttons, switches, and grips are learned to be touched may be consistent with Affordance proposed by Norman (1990).

Tactile enticement type	The original reasons of touch	Concrete elements or condition
Attracting attention	Fantastic shape	Fantastic shape
	With pattern or print	Circles pattern/ Small floral print/Check/Streak
	Vivid color	Red/Colorfulness
	Being obvious in the environment	Different style from environment. White in black background
Raising curiosity	Lack of information by vision	Unknown by vision. Being packaged
	Too particular to recognizing	Strange shape
	Something be hide	Cabinet /Drawer /Curtain
New experience providing	Texture trying	Smooth or rough cloth. Covers or real wood
	Function test	Slide track/Chair/Lamp
	With direction or description	Arrow indication. Product description or advertising.
	Trying novelty	Compound material New type product Different using way
Amusing interaction	Being playable	Stick-shape objects Toy/Stuffed toy
	Being operable	Handle shape Switch/Button/Cover
	With imagination or situation	Sofa bed Headgear-like shape
Friendly, kind feeling	Déjà vu / Familiar feeling	Owned or used before
	Lovely style	Small size/Circular shape Bright color Cute illustrations
	Natural material	Wood/Bamboo/Rattan
	Cleanness	Pure white
	Comfortable sense	Fluffy or loose shape Wool/fabric Matting white Pillow/Couch/Bed
Disapproval	Criticisms and doubts	The price doesn't match with the value. Improper application of material. Disagreeable using way.

Table1. Six aspects of Tactile Enticement.

Friendly and kind feeling

Natural materials, adorable things or comfortable objects are accessible. The feeling of comfortable actually based on visual aspect and experience, which makes people come closer and want to enjoy. For instance, fluffy stuffs, soft clothes or puffy shape are the characteristics that people may feel comfortable and intimate.

Besides, objects that look familiar or people have owned before could shorten the distance between object and people.

Disapproval

Object that is to subject disapproval could arouse the action, which is unexpected. Subject reflects that two reasons may cause the situation: first, is to give it a second chance to make sure if it is as unacceptable as it looked like. For example, a product with a high price however looks unworthy. The other one is criticism, which is necessary to feel it themselves.

SUSTAINABILITY OF TACTILE ENTICEMENT

During interview, if the motives of Tactile Enticement comes from curiosity and novel experience, most subjects state that they won't touch them again because they already got the information they want. In other words, these motives disappear as soon as they touch the objects. If the motives arouse from intimacy or amusing interactions, the object may likely to be touch again. In fact, the situation did happen that subjects touched the pillow twice when it appears twice on the route. Some subject state that it may be possible to touch these objects next time.

LIMITATION IN RESEARCH

There are still several defects in this research. To provide related research as reference, some are reviewed as follows:

- During exhibits-browsing experiment, the recording way is photographing. Photos could quickly be displayed to subjects in the follow-up interview, but they couldn't completely and exactly catch the process of touching behavior. In the meanwhile, adding video recording will be better.

- During interview, the content or the keywords said from subjects are the base for EGM. Therefore, the words said from subjects were able to affect the precision of Evaluation Grid Charts. "Tactile Enticement" is a new word that no well-defined expert could be interviewed, but selecting participants with well expression will help the result being exacter.

CONCLUSION

Objects with Tactile Enticement(TE) could be analyzed in six aspects—Attract Attention, Raise Curiosity, New Experience Provision, Amusing Interaction, Friendly and kind Feeling, and Disapproval. The visual characteristics of objects are categorized and shown at Table 1. "Attract Attention" is a backstage driving force of TE; Things that can "Raise Curiosity" would allow people to touch them out of curiosity. Something that is necessary to be experienced would also cause the reaction. "Amusing Interaction" of objects may also be the reason and relate to affordance. Intimate objects which are adorable and comfortable or natural may also easily to be touched. Finally, things that are disapproval may also have the ability to be touched.

These motivations, on the other hand, may decide whether the TE could be last long or not. Objects were touched out of curiosity and novelty may lose its TE quickly when the motive is satisfied. However, if things are intimate or Interesting in interaction would possibly arouse TE next time.

The result of this research could be used by designers to use the right elements on the products that frequently in contact with humans or needed to be touched. On the other hand, it could also be used to avoid the tactile enticement elements usage on untouchable objects or dangerous environment.

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